

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

UDC 635.522.2:631.847.211:581.557

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14730845>

EFFICIENCY OF INOCULATION OF BEANS OF DIFFERENT VARIETIES WITH NODULE BACTERIA

Abstract.

The study investigated the effectiveness of inoculating bean seeds of the Chervona Shapochka and Maslyana varieties with nodule bacteria *Rhizobium phaseoli* 700a under field conditions. An increase in the number, weight, and nitrogen-fixing activity of root nodules in inoculated plants was observed compared to the control group. Additionally, due to the active functioning of the symbiosis between the studied bean varieties and the selected bacterial strain, grain productivity increased by 11.4% and 17.2%, respectively. Further research on intensifying biological nitrogen fixation processes in bean agroecosystems is relevant, given the need to transition to environmentally sustainable agricultural production. The assimilation of atmospheric N₂ in plant-microbial systems is a key factor in reducing dependency on mineral nitrogen fertilizers and minimizing the anthropogenic impact on the environment.

Keywords: beans, inoculation, nodule bacteria, nitrogen-fixing activity, grain productivity.

Common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) is a traditional legume crop in Ukraine. In recent years, our country has significantly increased its bean exports, which was due to a steady increase in production volumes [5]. The special benefit of this crop is its nutritional value, namely the harmonious combination of high-quality protein with sugar, starch, minerals and essential amino acids. In addition, it contains vitamins A, B1, B2, B3, B6, C, carotene and an increased amount of vitamin E [8].

The development of innovative technologies aimed at optimizing nitrogen nutrition of plants and preserving soil fertility is one of the priorities of modern agriculture. This is due to the need to move to more sustainable and environmentally friendly farming systems [10].

Formation of highly productive bean crops is impossible without inoculation of seeds with bacterial preparations. Such treatment provides an increase in the efficiency of symbiotic nitrogen fixation, which makes it possible to significantly improve the level of realization of its genetic productivity potential [6, 7].

The share of the influence of pre-sowing inoculation of beans with rhizobia on grain yield can be as high as 22% [4]. At the same time, researchers have noted changes in the formation and functioning of symbiotic systems depending on the number of strains in the inoculant. It should be noted that both mono- and binary bacterization provided an increase in grain productivity [3].

The majority of microorganisms capable of forming nodules on bean roots in different regions of the world belong to the genus *Rhizobium*. In addition, they also include bacteria belonging to the genera *Ensifer* and *Pararhizobium* and a minority of *Bradyrhizobium*

species. These diazotrophs are alpha proteobacteria, but symbiosis with *P. vulgaris* has also been reported for some species belonging to the *Paraburkholderia* and *Cupriavidus* genera of beta proteobacteria [11]. That is, bean plants are capable of forming symbioses with different species of nitrogen-fixing microorganisms.

In view of the above, the aim of our work was to study the effectiveness of inoculation of bean seeds of different varieties with nodule bacteria in a field experiment.

Materials and methods. Bean plants of the Maslyana and Chervona Shapochka varieties were grown at the experimental field of the Institute of Plant Physiology and Genetics of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (IPPG NASU). For seed inoculation, the *R. phaseoli* 700a strain, stored in the collection of symbiotic and associative nitrogen-fixing microorganisms at the IPPG NASU, was used. The experiment was set up according to generally accepted methods [1].

The duration of seed bacterization was 60 minutes. The infectious load was 10⁹ cfu/ml. Sterile tap water was used as a control. Sowing was carried out in the first decade of June, in well-warmed soil to a depth of 4 cm. The area of the accounting plot was 5 m², the location of the plots was randomized.

Plants were sampled at the stages of budding and full flowering. Nitrogen-fixing activity (NFA) of bean root nodules was determined by the acetylene method [9]. The gas mixture was analyzed on a gas chromatograph "Agilent Technologies 6850" (USA) Network GC System. The gases were separated on a column (Supelco Porapak N) at a thermostat temperature of 55 °C and a detector temperature of 150 °C. The gas carrier was nitrogen (50 ml per 1 min).

Statistical processing of the experimental data was performed using Microsoft Excel 2019. The tables show the arithmetic mean data and their standard errors.

Results and discussion. It was found that pre-sowing treatment of bean seeds of Maslyana and Chervona Shapochka varieties with *R. phaseoli* 700a rhizobia provided an increase in the number and weight of nodules formed on the roots during the growing season compared to control plants. In Maslyana beans, the increase in the number of nodules on the roots and their

weight in the budding stage was 38.5 and 30.3%, while in the full flowering stage of the plants their growth was noted at the level of 9.6 and 27.7%. Inoculation with a selected strain of rhizobia had a more significant effect on the number of root nodules formed in symbiosis with plants of the Chervona Shapochka variety (Fig. 1, Table 1). At the same time, their mass indicators were higher compared to control plants by 31.1 and 7.4% in the budding and full flowering stages, respectively.

Fig. 1. Nodules on the roots of beans inoculated with *R. phaseoli* 700a. A) Maslyana variety; B) Chervona Shapochka variety (full flowering stage)

After analyzing the indicators of nitrogen-fixing activity of plants in the experiment, it was noted that they increased in plants of both bean varieties under bacterization conditions compared to control ones. The

increase in the studied parameters was 18.3 and 16.1% in Maslyana beans and 25.7 and 11.3% in Chervona Shapochka plants in the budding and full flowering stages, respectively (Table 1).

Table 1

Number, weight of root nodules and their nitrogen-fixing activity in bean plants of different varieties under inoculation with nodule bacteria

Variant	Plant development stage					
	budding			full flowering		
	number, pcs	weight, g	NFA, $\mu\text{mol C}_2\text{H}_4/(\text{plant}\cdot\text{hour})$	number, pcs	weight, g	NFA, $\mu\text{mol C}_2\text{H}_4/(\text{plant}\cdot\text{hour})$
Maslyana, without inoculation (control)	105.3 \pm 6.5	0.445 \pm 0.022	13.80 \pm 0.83	72.8 \pm 4.5	0.311 \pm 0.017	3.47 \pm 0.16
Maslyana + <i>R. phaseoli</i> 700a	145.8 \pm 7.9	0.580 \pm 0.029	16.33 \pm 0.90	79.8 \pm 5.0	0.397 \pm 0.022	4.03 \pm 0.20
Chervona Shapochka, without inoculation (control)	71.0 \pm 4.8	0.399 \pm 0.017	7.87 \pm 0.43	40.3 \pm 3.1	0.298 \pm 0.016	5.02 \pm 0.25
Chervona Shapochka + <i>R. phaseoli</i> 700a	126.5 \pm 6.4	0.523 \pm 0.025	9.89 \pm 0.52	57.5 \pm 3.8	0.320 \pm 0.020	5.59 \pm 0.34

The grain productivity of beans in the experiment under the conditions of introduction of *R. phaseoli* 700a into the agrocenosis was higher compared to control plants. In particular, the index of individual productivity of Maslyana bean plants exceeded the control plants by 17.2%. At the same time, in beans of the Chervona

Shapochka plants variety, the increase in this indicator compared to the control was 11.4%.

Due to the fact that natural strains are often able to compete in the process of nodule formation with bio-agents of microbial preparations introduced into agrocenoses, it is important to study soil populations of bean microsymbionts. This will make it possible to establish

the patterns of their formation and identify strains with agronomically useful properties [2]. In our work, bean plants of the studied varieties in the control variants formed a symbiosis with rhizobia present in the soil. Since the NFA indices of plants of these variants were quite high during the growing season, it is advisable to isolate nitrogen-fixing microorganisms from root nodules and further to determine their physiological, biochemical and symbiotic properties. Studies aimed at selecting effective strains for *P. vulgaris* in different soil and climatic zones under the influence of stress factors are promising, which can help mitigate the effects of climate change [11].

Conclusion. The study revealed an increase in the number, weight of root nodules, their nitrogen-fixing activity, and grain productivity of beans of the varieties Chervona Shapochka and Maslyana under their pre-sowing inoculation with nodule bacteria *Rhizobium phaseoli* 700a. Further study of biological nitrogen fixation of beans is of particular importance in connection with the need to transition to environmentally friendly agricultural production, since the involvement of natural mechanisms of N₂ fixation helps to reduce dependence on mineral fertilizers and reduce the anthropogenic burden on the environment.

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